

Employee Engagement at Kharanja Industry Pvt Ltd Humanbad

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Abstract- *The demand for paper is very large with increase in population this demand increases greatly the material for the paper industry is cellulose of woody plants and its conversion to paper and its products is the function pulp and paper industry . The tree are non renewable resource, the continuous use of trees for the purpose of papermaking will destroy forest and create environment imbalance, so one has think of alternative ways to minimize the use of trees for the purpose, so comes the ideas of recycling of waste papers to form the paper and paper products, that will minimize nearly 30% to 40% use of trees for paper making. Karajan industries pvt. Ltd. is also one which uses waste papers and recycles it to form a Kraft paper. The writing paper made of a high cane called papyrus, which grows along the zero rivers in Egypt. The cane flooring was glued wit starch. This head superior to veal and goat skin parchment, wax clay brick boards and other writing material available at hate time. Sothern Europe learned of the process and began producing waste paper in the late 17th century, and a paper mill was founded in the United States in 1960. At that time, the entire European manuscript mill was made of strand rags and line. Book printing began with the Gutenberg Bible and greatly increased the demand for paper. Arund 1750, the whip was developed and adopted in Holland, when it became Hollander. In 1799, a Frenchman Robert invented the course of form sheets of paper in a metal screen in motion throughout evolution and improvement; this has turned out to be today'sfourth engine machine.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the year 1983, the Karajan industries pvt ltd stared its operation in Bidar district. Because backward area the government had given the subsidy to start Karajan industries operations for developing this area and the company had seen the availability of the raw material, transportation, market opportunities, cheap labor and

well water resource etc.

A large number of expansion programs and expansion of capacity with an outlay of Rs. 10000 cores have been announced covering the various sectors like paper, paper board, newsprint etc. The Indian economy is progressing well and targeting 8%+ growth. The economic reforms coupled with the liberalized government policies: India today offers excellent business opportunity for investments. One of the first FDI projects may come through the proposed finish proposal to set up 400000 ton capacity plant with an investment of US\$ 240 million. The expanding industrial scenario calls for efforts to tackle related problems: Industry needs capital and technology. Since energy cost accounts nearly 25% of cost of production there is an urgency to improve energy management and energy consumption.

Quantum jump in production, called for by the demand projection is possible only by expansion of existing capacity and creation of additional capacity. Up gradation of technology and new capacities also involve massive investment.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Importance of representative commitment of members of staff engagement:

It is a benefit which demonstrates the communicated or connection between the employee and the employer in their specific association. A allied with worker a person who wholly observed by the best administration how individual is association with his or her respective work.

A relationship with high employees communicated cangive the higher productivity. Representative commitment at first should up an idea in association

speculation in the 1990's... getting the opportunity to be discernibly sweeping in association rehearse in the 200s, yet it remains tested.

The theory of employees participation represents the way to achieve the strategic goal of the company by creating the circumstance for the well being of human resources and for every employee, manager and executive manager the dedicate himself completely to his work to offer the best hard work in the best interest of the business .

Theory of employee engagement it starts seems just wide spread sense. According to the theory, the leaders of an organization must make sure that all members of their staff are fully affianced.

Let all your staff members be flying involved and have their work completely changed. The ideal is that the staff is engaged in the same way that entrepreneurs are interested in the work so as to really attract your best attention and inspire you to do your best. Employee involvement is more than the rudiments that contain: It is easy to confuse commitment with other concepts that are simply similar. The concepts are job happiness, employees engagement and employee account ability. The first of these is that employers should strive to make employees feel happy and comfortable at work in the workplace.

Employee taking parts is the theory that is a bit similar to employee engagement, but does not completely match. The commitment focuses more or on the condition of creating the compulsion in which the worker will feel completed to work.

Employee input is the most touching option, expected at exploit the positive thinking of employee. Empowerment is the idea you necessitate to give your recruits the influence to make business decisions. Emancipation cannot act as a helpful force, regardless of other efforts to engage the culture of commitments. Only those workers who are adequately involved can be authoritative, which bring us back side to the general centrality of the commitment.

- **NEED FOR THE STUDY**

The employee engagement study provide the information about the performance ranks, basis on

which decisions regarding salary fixation, confirmation, promotion, transfer, demotion are taken. The study provide feedback information about the levels of achievements and behavior of sub ordinate this information helps to review the performance of the subordinates, rectifying the performance deficiencies and to set new standards of work if necessary.

The study also provides the information to diagnose deficiency in employee regarding skill, knowledge, determine training and developmental needs and to prescribe the means for employee growth provides information for correcting the placement.

- **OBJECTIVE**

- To know when employees are engaged they will know well about the company vision and mission.
- To know the employees working condition, selection process, training process in the Karajan industries private limited.
- To know the overall functioning of the organization like production process etc.
- To know the how employees emotionally connected with the Karajan industries pvt. Ltd.
- To know engagement helps to keep good communication between employee and employers.

- **SCOPE OF THE STUDY**

- The scope of the study is concerned to the Karajan pvt ltd. Bidar.
- It helps the management to improve employees working condition.
- The study will provide the solution to the management by understanding the provided by the management.
- To measure the viability when the association does not satisfy the representative's requisition.

III. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table number: 1

Number of responds with different engagement program

gender	No of responds	Proportion
Male	97	97%
Female	03	03%
Total	100	100%

Graph number: 1 number of respondents with different gender

INTERPRETATION

From the above table it was found that 97% of male employees said that engagement program was helpful in career development 3% of female employees said that employees said that Employee engagement is not helpful for career development

Table number: 2 ANALYSES

The above graph shows that the male employees Responds more than the female for developing the career

Age	No of respondent's	%
18-25	09	13
25-35	45	53
35-45	35	24
45 and above	11	10
Total	100	100

Graph no: 2 number of respondent with different age group

INTERPRETATION

The above chart explains that 9 % belong to the group 18-25, 53% belongs 25-35, 24% between 35-45and 10percent is above 45 age group

Table number -3

Since how many years employees have been engaged with this factory

No of years	no of respondent's	%
1yrs to 10yrs	43	43
11yrs to 20yrs	07	07
21yrs to 30yrs	14	14
31 to 40 yrs	10	10
41 to 50 yrs	11	11
51above	15	15
Total	100	100

Graph number -3 no of years employees have been engaged with this factory

Interpretation

From the above table it was found that 43% of employees said that employees works was excellent, 7% of employees said that training program was good, 14% of employees said that training program bad, remaining 10% of employees said that training program was normal

Table number-4

Type of communication strategy prevails in your engagement

Types of communication	No of respondent	%
Upward communication	40	40
Downward communication	15	15
Horizontal communication	45	45
Diagonal communication	00	00
Total	100	100

Graph number-4 type of communication strategy prevails in your engaged

Interpretation

The table shows that, horizontal communication is been followed in the organization

Table Number-5

Education of Employees

Education of employees	No of respondent's	%
SSLC	18	18
NO SSLC	2	02

PUC	40	40
DEGREE	40	40
ITI DEPLOMA	10	10
Total	100	100

Graph No-5 Type of education of employees

INTERPRETATION

From the above table it was found that 18% of employees' feedback was excellent during the training program 2% of employees feedback was good, 40% of employees feedback is average and 10% of employees' feedback was poor

Table -6

How many employees are satisfied with the present salary?

Satisfied salary employees	No respondent	%
Satisfied	90	90
Unsatisfied	10	10
Total	100	100

Graph numbers -6 are employees satisfied with present salary

INTERPRETATION

From the above that the organization pay by considering the work to satisfied and unsatisfied

Table Number-7

How fascinating the work in the engaged environment

Motivating to work	Number of respondent	%
Externally motivating	50	50
Fairly motivating	50	50
Total	100	100

Graph No-7 How Fascinating the work in the Engaged Environment

INTERPRETATION

The above table shows that 50% of respondent feel they are extremely motive

Table Number-8

Is the harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karajan Ltd?

Harmonious relationship	No of respondents	%
Yes	100	100
NO	0	00
TOTAL	100	100

Graph No-8

Is there harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karanja Ltd

INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows the 100% of harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karajan ltd

Table Number-9

Do you feel secured in your job?

Feel secured in job	No of respondent's	proportion
Yes	100	100
No	0	00
Total	100	100

Graph No-10

Is there harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karanja Ltd

INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows the 100% of harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karajan ltd

Table Number-10

Employee income level

Employee income level	No of respondent	%
5000-10000	00	00

10000-15000	25	25
15000-20000	50	50
20000-30000	15	15

Graph No-10

Is there harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karanja Ltd

INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows the 100% of harmonious relationship with your colleagues in Karanja Ltd

Table number-11

Is Karanja providing the equal facilities to their employees?

Stated objective and Resources	No of respondent	Proportion
yes	100	100
No	00	00
Total	100	100

Graph no: 11 Is Karanja provide the equal facilities to their employees?

INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that, the Karanja Ltd provide the equal facilities to their employees

Table number-12

Employee income level

Employee income level	No of respondent	%
5000-10000	00	00
10000-15000	25	25
15000-20000	50	50
20000-30000	15	15
30000above	10	10
Total	100	100

Graph No -12 Employees Income Level

INTERPRETATION

The above chart shows that, the employee income level 10000 to 15000 (20%), 15000 to 20000(25%), 20000 to 30000(15%), 30000above (10%)

IV. FINDING

- The Karanja pvt ltd maintaining the good and healthy relationship with their co workers
- Majority of employees (80) believe that company helped them to build their skills sets providing training and that is valuable
- The organization pays salary based on the employees work and experience not on qualification
- The employee work condition is sufficient for employees

- It was found that majority of respondents employees belong to the age group 30 to 40
- Employees (85%) believe that senior level management is open, transparent and open in communication
- Employees (85%) believes that their company is great place to work Employee's relationship with other department is also good
- The superior of the organization treat employees as a friend guide them properly and friendly

CONCLUSION

The Karajan private limited running in the area of sindmandgi, Bidar district since 1983. The companies have the proper management system and the good working condition the workers in the organization were happy with the organization policies the employees are satisfied with the wage and salary in the organization. The Karajan private limited have the great employees engagement system one of the representative are exceptionally are cheerful to work in this organization, it keeps great communication between its colleagues, administration and also between the superior and its subordinators. The organization\factory have the wide space of land so it providing the many facilities like restrooms, parking facilities, greater office and canteen facilities at lower price. The employee's engagement study carried out in Karajan craft industries pvt.Ltd was successful in achieving specific objective with their employee's co-operation.

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